

Zero-Energy Devices for 6G: First Real-Time Indoor Localization Thanks to Ambient Backscattering of Commercial 4G UEs

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Abstract— Traditional approaches for indoor localization of smartphones, such as Wi-Fi signal strength, and Bluetooth low energy (BLE) localization techniques, face limitations like energy consumption and costly infrastructure deployment. This paper presents a novel indoor localization system, based on zero-energy devices (ZED) which are energy-autonomous (powered by light), and based on ambient backscatter communication (AmBC) technique which re-uses ambient mobile networks infrastructures and waves. Uplink pilot signals broadcasted by user equipment (UEs) are backscattered by ZEDs close by, and base stations (BS) detect the ZED message in the received UL pilot signal. We implement two scenarios of our localization system. In the first scenario, ZEDs are fixed with known locations in rooms and the location of the UE (a smartphone) carried by a moving user is tracked. In the second variant, the UEs (4G modems) are fixed and in known locations, and the location of the flexible ZED worn by a moving user is tracked. We demonstrate the two scenarios, in real-time, in a real indoor environment, with 4th Generation (4G) commercial UEs (4G smartphone and 4G modem) and a 4G software defined radio base station. We achieve room-based detection accuracy.

Keywords—6G, Indoor localization, ambient backscatter, LTE, IoT.

I. INTRODUCTION

Location-aware personal services such as indoor navigation rely on indoor localization of smartphones or radio frequency tags worn by moving people. Different techniques such as Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID), Wi-Fi, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), and Ultrawideband (UWB) based indoor localization, have emerged over time, each with its own benefits and trade-offs in accuracy, cost, power consumption and infrastructure needs. An RFID reader deployed in a building locates RFID passive or active tags (worn by people) by leveraging the angle of arrival (AoA) and phase of arrival (PoA) estimation techniques [1]. However, such system requires a dense deployment of RFID readers in buildings, hence with high operational costs. Wi-Fi-based localization of smartphones utilizes fingerprinting of smartphone's received signal strength indicator (RSSI). While Wi-Fi is an all-purpose technique, since Wi-Fi networks are everywhere, it does endure signal fluctuation and multipath fading, limiting fingerprinting corresponding

position accuracy to ± 5 -15 m [2,3]. Furthermore, while smartphones localization by BLE beacons deployed in buildings have higher accuracy (± 1 m), BLE beacons frequently need their batteries to be replaced to ensure proper performance [4]. Alternatively, UWB has centimeter-level accuracy (± 10 cm), which supports its application in high-precision tracking applications. However, the hardware cost and power consumption of UWB limit its widespread use [5]. Finally, mobile network based indoor localization methodologies have been studied based on Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA), and Channel State Information (CSI) [6]. Still, these techniques require a dense deployment of femtocells, leading to a high infrastructure cost.

In parallel, the concept of zero-energy device (ZED), or Ambient internet-of-thing (IoT) device has been introduced in discussions on the evolutions of the 5th Generation (5G) networks in standardization [7] and in European Research Hexa-X I and II Flagship projects on the 6th Generation (6G) networks [8,9]. ZEDs are energy-autonomous IoT devices, capable of harvesting ambient energy to power ultra-low power circuits.

To overcome the issues of the aforementioned existing localization approaches, or at least to provide a complementary solution in a multi-modal localization approach [3] (i.e. combining several sources of localization information), one variant of ZED, based on ambient backscatter communication (AmBC) in mobile networks, has been proposed to achieve low-power and low-cost indoor localization of smartphones [10], conceptually. In [10], at least one ZED beacon is deployed in each room of a building. The ZED position in the building is known and reported on a map. The ZED backscatters ambient signals exchanged between the smartphone and the BS. Each time, a ZED message is detected by the smartphone (or the BS) the room-based location of the smartphone is deduced. Unlike in previously mentioned techniques, a ZED beacon broadcasts its identity (ID) message by modulating an already existing ambient radio frequency (RF) signal, hence without requiring a dedicated RF source. In contrast to RFID requiring a dense network of active readers or active BLEs beacons relying on battery-powered beacons, the ZED harvests energy and reflects ambient mobile network signals to broadcast its message [11] and advantageously does not require extra infrastructure to be deployed.

However, detection sensitivity especially in dense multi-ZED environments is a challenge that requires appropriate signal processing techniques [12,13]. In [10], the concept is assessed through ray tracing simulations for downlink (DL) AmBC, where smartphones detect ZEDs in downlink ambient signals from BSs. However, the same concept is also applicable in uplink (UL), as explained in [14]. Long Range (LoRa) backscatter room-based localization [15] follows the same principle. However, LoRa networks are not widely deployed worldwide and have a lower global coverage than mobile networks.

AmBC concept applies to all mobile networks generations and has first been implemented and tested with the ambient 4th Generation (4G), which is until now, the generation with the largest coverage world-wide. AmBC has been tested successfully on both long-term evolution (LTE) downlink signals [16-20] or more recently LTE UL signals [21,22]. In particular, these very recent works have shown that ZED in the proximity of a 4G commercial smartphone can be detected by a software-defined radio (SDR) BS, simply by listening to UL LTE sounding reference symbols (SRS) signals regularly sent by the smartphones. Such ZEDs backscatter incident LTE signals embedding unique identifiers through Gold pseudo-noise sequences, so that BS recognizes them, without any active transmissions [21]. In [21], a correlation algorithm is proposed to distinguish the backscattered signal from background noise. [21] focuses on the performance evaluation of backscatter-based detection, including maximum range evaluation, system scalability, and detection reliability.

However, up to now, indoor localization based on AmBC as conceptually introduced in [10] has never been tested experimentally, in real-world environment, in real-time, yet.

Backscatter communication is gaining momentum in cellular standardization, as introduced in 3GPP Release 18 and studied further in Release 19 under the Ambient IoT work item. Further discussions are also expected to continue in Release 20. Positioned at the intersection of 5G Advanced and 6G, this technology plays a key role in shaping future network capabilities. Notably, Hexa-X II, Europe’s flagship 6G project [8,9], highlights ambient backscatter and energy-efficient localization as essential to future sustainable networks. Our work contributes directly to this direction by offering a practical, low-power localization system aligned with the 6G vision.

For the first time, in this paper, we demonstrate experimentally, in a real indoor environment, the feasibility of AmBC based localization scheme as conceptually introduced in [10]. Two scenarios are demonstrated. In Demonstration 1, ZED beacons are placed in known locations and a moving user wearing a smartphone is localized each time it is close to a ZED. In Demonstration 2, 4G modems are placed in known locations and a moving user wearing a ZED is localized each time it gets close to a 4G modem. Our proof-of-concept runs in real-time, with 4G commercial smartphones (for Demonstration 1) and 4G modems (for Demonstration 2) of the shelf, LTE standard ambient SRS signals from the smartphone as ambient RF sources, a software defined radio LTE BS. As ZED beacons, we use ZED prototypes which are energy-autonomous and which harvest light energy.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents our system design and implementation. Section III our preliminary experimental results and analysis. Section IV concludes this paper.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN & IMPLEMENTATION

The indoor localization system demonstrated in this paper is a practical realization of the concept outlined in [10]. Unlike [10], which simulates DL ambient backscatter communication (AmBC), our system operates in the UL using LTE SRS. Prior works like [14] typically treat smartphones as readers of DL-backscattered signals, whereas in our design, smartphones act as assisting nodes, transmitting UL signals that are modulated (backscattered) by passive ZEDs. This key distinction shifts the complexity away from the user device, requiring no modification to commercial off-the-shelf smartphones. All intelligence and processing are handled at the BS, which is implemented via software-only modifications on an SDR platform, without any hardware changes to the mobile network. The experimental validation builds upon our setup introduced in [21], confirming the feasibility of accurate room-level localization with minimal infrastructure. Two variants are tested, which are presented hereafter.

In Demonstration 1, prototypes of ZEDs with known locations are installed as fixed beacons deployed in a real building to broadcast their ID. In this case, a moving user with a smartphone is located each time it gets close to a ZED and the BS detects the ZED message in the UL SRS signal.

In Demonstration 2, prototypes of ZEDs as moving beacons are worn by a moving user, and 4G modems are deployed in the building with known locations. In this case, the moving user is located each time it gets close to a ZED and that the BS detects the ZED in the 4G modem SRS signal.

Sub-Section A presents our system architecture, Sub-Section B presents our ZED and Sub-Section C presents our SDR based SRS extraction implementation and backscatter detection of the ZED.

Fig. 1. System Components

A. System Architecture

Whatever the demonstration setup, the localization system as illustrated in Fig. 1 consists of the following components:

- One User Equipment (UE), i.e. a commercial 4G smartphone (for Demonstration 1) or a 4G model (for demo2) transmitting UL SRS signals.
- Several ZEDs that backscatter and modulate incident LTE SRS signals using Gold Code sequences.
- One SDR based LTE BS (using USRP B210) that extracts SRS signals and detects modulated responses, with code that we developed starting from the open-source project srsRAN [23].
- Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) Server & Godot User Interface (UI) [24], to provide a real-time localization visualization system that tracks UE movement within an indoor environment.

B. ZED prototypes and ZED Gold Code Assignment and Generation

The demonstration set-up uses passive ZEDs, as depicted in Fig. 2. The passive Tag on the left is used for Demonstration 1 whereas the flexible tag on the right is used for Demonstration 2. ZEDs modulate LTE SRS passively, reflecting or absorbing incident signals, thereby enciphering their existence. Its electronic components (an RF switch and a micro-controller) is powered thanks to a solar panel. The design, performance and autonomy is similar to the ones of the prototypes depicted and assessed in [14].

Fig. 2. Tag/ZED

For both types, each ZED is assigned with a unique Gold Code sequence for rigorous cross-correlation separation. The key parameters include: 31-bit length for robust cross-correlation; 7 times bit repetition to improve detection. Hence, the total sequence duration is given by:

$$31 \times 7 \times 10 \text{ ms} = 2.17 \text{ s, per cycle.}$$

Each ZED operates in a predefined time slot, minimizing interference while maintaining accurate localization.

C. ZEDs backscattering of LTE UL SRS and real-time detection by SDR BS

When a UE (moving in Demonstration 1 and fixed in a room in demo2) gets close to a ZED (fixed in a room in Demonstration 1 and moving in demo2), the ZED backscatters and modulates the UL LTE SRS of the UE. It modulates the signal by toggling between reflective and absorptive states, imprinting the

backscattered signal with a unique Gold Code sequence. Based on these backscattering, the srsRAN SDR BS instantly identifies the interacting ZED in real-time as illustrated in Fig. 3. The srsRAN BS, implemented using a USRP B210, continuously extracts and processes these UL SRS signals.

Fig. 3. ZED backscattering and detection

The system uses a customized version of srsRAN, an open-source LTE stack, to extract UL SRS signals for backscatter-based localization of the UE.

The srsRAN codebase was altered to support SRS signal extraction, allowing the system to analyze UL SRS modulations to perform ZED detection. To ensure accurate tracking of the moving UE in Demonstration 1 and the moving ZED in Demonstration 2, the sampling rate is configured to capture periodic SRS sequences every 10ms, aligning with the transmission interval of the UE. With this setup, the system continuously records and processes SRS data, facilitating reliable detection of modulated signals from the ZEDs.

A moving average filter with a window length of 5 samples (50ms) is applied to the signals to reject outliers and improve detection accuracy while decreasing false positives. This algorithm (detailed in [21]) allows transient noise not to take effect on Just-in-Time Localization performance. Also, the same Median Filtering is applied to the SRS fluctuations to smooth out rough changes in the amplitude, reducing the impact of rapid variations and keeping the signal stable. SRS signals are captured, and a Correlation-Based Detection (CBD) is applied using Gold Codes that have already been stored in the system, allowing the system to reliably identify passive ZED devices by matching their unique backscattering pattern codes within the captured SRS signals.

D. TCP Server & Godot UI for Real-Time Visualisation of Localization

The system utilizes a socket TCP client-server to link srsRAN and the Godot-based UI and track the UE movement in demo1 or the ZED movement in Demonstration 2, in real-time inside the indoor environment. The following data flow has been implemented and run in real-time: first, the user enters a room (step 1), and the UL SRS of the UE (step 2) interacts with the ZED device and the srsRAN BS recognizes the matching Gold Code; then (step3) a TCP message is sent from the srsRAN SDR BS to the localization TCP server; finally (step4) Godot UI is updated in real-time, showing visually the user current location (which is estimated as being the fixed UE location in Demonstration 1 or the ZED location in Demonstration 2).

The following TCP Message Format is used: {UE_ID, Location_ID, Timestamp} where, UE_ID indicates a Unique ID of the user's device; ZED_ID Identifies the ZED device, and Timestamp is the Timestamp of detection.

The Godot UI provides real-time tracking updates, visually displaying the user's movement between rooms while integrating location updates received via TCP communication from the BS. More precisely, real-Time UE tracking visualization is implemented as follows. Based on the location of the UE, the Godot UI updates the 3D indoor map in real-time to provide a visual indication of location as the UE moves from room to room. Location updates have an associated color-coded room state, indicating which room the current point is in and whether it is an entry or an exit event caused by a timeout mechanism that identifies if no further movements occur. Additionally, the TCP Server processes and logs all movement data, enabling post-analysis for tracking patterns, enhancing system accuracy, and optimizing localization performance.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS & ANALYSIS

This section presents our experimental demonstration results. Two scenarios are demonstrated.

A. Demonstration 1: Indoor Localization with Passive ZEDs

1) Deployment and Demonstration Scenario

In this demonstration scenario, we deploy the indoor localization system with three ZEDs located in three different rooms (room 1, room 2 and room 3), as illustrated in Fig. 4. The BS is an indoor 4G femtocell. A user is moving with the 4G commercial UE (a smartphone) throughout the building. The maximum range between the BS and the UE is 20 meters. Each ZED is assigned a Gold Code sequence for differentiation, as described in Section II-B. To keep track of room entry and transitions, the system continuously monitors UL LTE SRS signals as UE-carrying users move between rooms, as explained in Section II-C. The detection process described in Section II-C is implemented with the UE transmitting UL SRS every 10ms. By associating the received SRS signals with predefined Gold Codes, the srsRAN BS can identify which ZED is in contact with the UE and accurately pinpoint and locate the user within the Godot UI in real-time, as described in Section II-D.

2) Results and observed limitations

As illustrated in Fig. 5, the user carrying the UE walks through the building going successively in Room 1, Room 2 and Room 3. To enable us to check the accuracy of the detection, the user wears a video camera on his forehead to visually capture in real-time in which room he actually is and allow comparison with the localization displayed by the Godot UI.

For instance, in Fig. 5-a), the upper right corner of the figure shows the Godot UI, and the location of the UE, as detected by the localization system, in real-time. We can observe that the system locates the UE in room 1, which is the printer room. On the upper right side of Fig. 5-a), we show what the user actually sees, at the same exact instant, simultaneously, thanks to the

camera he wears on his forehead. We can observe that he sees the printer of Room 1. Hence, we can check that the system successfully locates the UE in Room 1.

Fig. 4. Plane View for Our Setup

Similarly, in Fig. (5-b) we observe that when the user encounters his colleagues having a meeting in Room 2 (meeting room), as illustrated by the upper right part of the figure, simultaneously, the Godot UI displays his location in Room 2 (as illustrated by the lower-left part of the figure). Finally, in Fig. 5-c), when the user sees the desk in Room 3 (meeting room), as illustrated by the right part of the figure, he is simultaneously localized by the Godot UI in Room 3 (as illustrated again by the left-lower part of the figure). Finally, the ZED-UE distance range to trigger detection has been measured to reach up to 0.5 to 1 meter, Results were averaged over 10 trials per room,

showing consistent room-level accuracy with detection delay maintained at ~ 4.5 s.

The full live Demonstration has been filmed, and the video of the Demonstration is available online [25].

a) Room 1 (printer room) localisation accuracy checking

b) Room 2 (meeting room) localisation accuracy checking

c) Room 3 (meeting room) localisation accuracy checking

Fig. 5. Real-time checking of accuracy of the localization of the UE worn by the moving user in a) Room 1, b) Room2 and c) Room 3.

Regarding the processing delay of our testbed of localization system, we observe that at least two complete cycles of a Gold Code (~ 4.34 seconds) are necessary for the system to reliably detect and give a needed localization confirmation and avoid false positives. In practice, the system required a delay of around 4.5 seconds to accurately determine which ZED location was correct, matching the expected time to process the Gold Codes correlation. A key limitation of the current detection process is that to localize correctly, the user must be stationary for at least one complete cycle of the Gold Code sequence (2.17s per cycle,

4.34s for detection). Continuous movement during this period introduces channel effects, like Doppler (shift) and multipath (fading) involving the time displacement of multiple paths would cause distortions in the correlation between two backscattered signals and impede the detection performance during this period. This limitation comes into play for real-time tracking, as moving quickly from one location to another before completing an entire cycle through the sequence can lead to incomplete or inaccurately pulled detections. Indeed, with a steady UE, we reached a UE-ZED distance of 5 meters.

Finally, the current version of srsRAN does not support multiple users yet, although the LTE standard does support reception of SRS from multiple users. So, for now, with this experimental set-up it is not yet possible to support multi-user localization and identification.

In summary, the moving UE is localized through its contacts with ZEDs, as long as the moving UE is within a distance of up to 1 meter from the ZEDs.

B. Demonstration 2: Indoor Localization with Movable Flexible Wearable ZED and Fixed 4G Modem

Fig. 6. Flexible Wearable ZED

1) Deployment and Demonstration Scenario

In this demonstration scenario, the user wears a flexible tag as ZED. In this scenario, the UE is a fixed 4G modem in a known location (a room) from the localization system. On the contrary, the ZED is moving, and its location has to be tracked by the system. When the ZED gets close to the UE, the localization system deduces that the ZED is in the same room as the fixed UE. Since this version of our localization system depends on multiple 4G modems, it inherently involves higher infrastructure complexity and increased deployment costs.

The experimental setup for this demonstration consists of a 4G modem UE connected to the srsRAN BS, serving as the primary signal source for localization. The experimental set-up described in Section II, is implemented, with a 4G modem as UE.

As srsRAN does not yet support multi-user SRS extraction (even though the standard allows it), we emulated the deployment of 4G modems in each room of the building, by re-using the same and single 4G modem UE, each time we ran a test in each room. So, for now, we could not yet test in real-time,

the full trajectory of one user walking through a building and being detected by distinct 4G modems deployed in distinct rooms, one after the other. We could only test in real-time, for each room separately, that the user presence was detected in the room.

2) Observations & Results

Similar results as for Demonstration 1 have been found. However, per room separately. Again, we observe that, it takes the system a minimum of two full Gold Code cycles (approximately 4.34 seconds) to reliably determine the user's position. In practical experiments, the actual tracking delay was found to be around 4.5s, matching that of the detection delay that was observed for Demonstration 1.

In summary, in Demonstration 2, an equal ZED-UE detection range and delay as for Demonstration 1, is observed.

IV. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

This work demonstrates a real-time, an indoor localization system without dedicated power and RF sources thanks to ambient LTE SRS and passive ZEDs, with standard non-custom UE (e.g., commercial 4G phones and 4G modems without firmware alterations or specific hardware). Two scenarios of the system have been tested. In Demonstration 1, one ZED beacon is deployed per room with a fixed and known location, and the moving user wearing a 4G smartphone presence in the room is detected by the system when the message of the ZED of the room is detected by the BS. In Demonstration 2, the moving user is wearing a flexible ZED and a 4G modem is put in a room with a known location. When the system detects the ZED message in the 4G modem signal, it deduces that the user is in the room of the 4G modem. The experimental results exhibit room-based localization accuracy. Also, we observe that with current setup, a detection delay of ~4.5 seconds is required to guarantee stable identification due to the Gold Code cycle time requirement.

Despite this very promising and preliminary proof-of-concept of this localization system, several challenges remain, some linked to the current version of srsRAN, which does not support all standardized LTE features. In future works, optimizing signal processing algorithms, improving real-time localization efficiency, robustness to mobility, multi-user detection and AI-based filtering methods could enhance this technique for large-area applications.

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